

A STUDY ON TOTAL QUALITY MANAGEMENT - A DEVELOPMENT OF QUESTIONNAIRE AND PILOT-TESTING

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Abstract

It is well documented that Total Quality Management is need of the present and future society. The objective was to validate and develop an instrument to assess the awareness and practices towards TQM in the Greater Mumbai population. A pilot study was conducted to measure perception of 30 Principals towards TQM in Greater Mumbai including all three Zones. Reliability testing in terms of test-retest, internal consistency, and content validity was performed. A panel of nine experts from education field evaluated the research instrument for content validity and it was found to have strong content item validity (Indices = 1). Each domain of Total Quality Management showed good internal consistency of Cronbach's Alpha 0.961 for TQM. The instrument established sound reliability and validity and, therefore, can be an effective tool to measure knowledge and practices of the general population towards Total Quality Management in any Educational Institute, and can help Principals the administrative heads to ensure quality management in their respective institute.

Keywords: *Total Quality Management, TQM, ISO 9001:2015, Reliability, validity.*

1. Background:

The quality revolution was started by W. Edwards Deming, a student of Shewart, who introduced a clever twist to his teacher's theory of shifting so as to check the quality analysts from the inspection stage to the inception stage. Quality has been focused as one of the utmost serious concerns that organizations have concentrated on in the last 20 to 30 years (Rajaram & Sivakumar, 2008).^{*1} In former times education was restricted to limited people and more of spiritual learning was encouraged. India being

a democratic nation guarantees everyone equal opportunities for getting better education. The Education Commission of India while clarifying the significance of education in the monetary and social change of India, remarked that the fate of India is currently being formed in classrooms (NCERT, 2006). The Relevance of Dr. Sarvapalli Radhakrishnan's educational thoughts cited by (Behera, 2015)^{*2} in his research is "India being an emerging country has gained ground in numerous territories like farming, industry, transport, sciences and innovation including the innovation for space travel. To proceed with this advancement, India needs taught residents, the essential of which is most likely "Universal literacy" or "Universalization of Education". Current educational exploration has demonstrated that school has been changed into a learning association which should be an all-around organized institution and should recharge itself ceaselessly considering its present and future needs. Even though there is progress in elementary education in India but there are quality issues that need to be addressed.

As per United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) report on Human Development Index (HDI), "India's 2013 HDI value has improved from 0.369 to 0.586 since 1980, which falls in the average human development group -positioning the country at 135 from among 187 countries" (NDTV, 2013).^{*3}

2. Aims And Objectives:

The aims and objective of the current study was to develop a questionnaire to measure Perspective towards Total Quality Management and Organizational Effectiveness of any educational institute. Reliability as well as validity of developed questionnaire/instrument was established. The final version of the questionnaire/instrument will also help to measure Perspective towards Total Quality Management and Organizational Effectiveness of any educational institute.

3. Operational Definition Of The Terms:

- **Total Quality Management:** it's going to be defined as a group of practices throughout the organization, geared to make sure the organization consistently meets or exceeds students' requirements, which is measured under the dimensions of Context of the Organization, Academic Leadership, Planning, Support to total quality management, Operations by school management, Performance evaluation, Improvement for quality management and also it is an art of organizing the entire to realize excellence.

4. Methods:

4.1 Total Quality Management (Tqm):

- **Questionnaire Development:**

The questionnaire is used for data collection to measure perspective of administrative heads and supervisor's. The initial questionnaire of Total Quality Management (TQM) is adapted from requirement listed by ISO 9001:2015. Hence researcher had interviewed Mr. Shyam Sharma, who is Managing Director of Shamkri's an ISO Certification Body. For the purpose of adaptation and reframing of the questionnaire, a set criterion was followed, developed by ISO 9001:2015 standards. In the Initial step the set criterion suggested by ISO 9001:2015 standards was reframed according to the research need.

Reliability of Understanding of Organizational Effectiveness tool:

Table 4.1 shows the reliability index of the Understanding of ICT tool.

Tool	Cronbach's Alpha
Total Quality Management	0.961

Reliability of Understanding of ICT tool:

The investigator considered it important to measure reliability of the scale towards observation of TQM which is a part of the any educational institute. The tool was provided to a representative sample of 30 administrative heads from English Medium Secondary Schools of Greater Mumbai. The investigator prepared the tool and got it validated from nine experts. Cronbach's Alpha was used to measure and find the internal consistency of the tool. From the results the researcher got the Alpha value which was 0.961 which is the strongest acceptance level and hence permitted the researcher to use the scale as an instrument to measure the effectiveness of the TQM to attain reliable results. Hence, the rating scale is valid and reliable. The total numbers of items in the tool are 67 under 7 Dimensions of TQM.

Table 4.2 For Reliability Statistics including dimension of TQM.

Item Reliability Statistics including dimension of TQM		
	item-rest correlation	if item dropped Cronbach's α
Context of Organization	0.743	0.965
Leadership	0.858	0.955
Planning in QMS	0.928	0.949
Support to total quality management	0.924	0.949
Operation	0.898	0.951
Performance Evaluation	0.803	0.960
Improvement	0.939	0.948

Figure 4.1 Pearson Correlation among dimension of TQM

Scoring of Total Quality Management (TQM) tool:

For the purpose of this analysis, quantification of responses is needed in order to analyze the data using statistical techniques. A five point scale has been used by the researcher for the responses required for each of the items in the tool. The five point scale is as follows: Always, Very Often, Sometimes, Rarely, Never. Table 4.3 shows the response

category and inventory values of items of Total

Quality Management.

Table 4.3 For items, which are positively worded, the weightage given is as

Follows:-

Response Category	Always	Very often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
Scale value	5	4	3	2	1

There are 67 positively worded items in Total Quality Management tool. The lowest possible score for each individual on the scale is 67 and the highest possible score is 335.

5. Pilot Study:

This included establishing the face validity and content validity of the research tool. For the present research, face validity and content validity of the pre-test and post-test have been determined. The face validity and content validity of all the tools were determined by obtaining the opinion of 9 experts in the field of Education on the relevance and representatives of each item. The items were retained and modified as per the expert comments. After that, a pilot study was conducted to assess the tool's reliability. The ability of an instrument to accurately calculate the phenomenon it was intended to measure is referred to as reliability. It is synonymous with consistency or repeatability. A measurement is said to be accurate if it produces consistent results over time. The pilot study was conducted among English medium secondary schools of Greater Mumbai. The investigator approached the administrative heads and collected the data from them using online Google forms. The data was collected using online mode due to the lock down situation during Covid-19. The purpose and procedure for filling out the Google form was well explained to the administrative heads and supervisors via Google form only in order to avoid any disturbances while filling and submitting the online Google form.

6. Conclusions:

The developed questionnaire for this pilot study was a valid and reliable instrument for assessment of practices towards Total Quality Management. The current questionnaire can serve as a useful tool in research to measure knowledge and practices of the general population towards Total Quality Management in any Educational Institute, and can help Principals the administrative heads to ensure quality management in their

institute. With the help of this questionnaire administrative head will be able to understand the requirements of TQM to be maintained in their institute. To conclude, the study shows encouraging findings, and generates testimony of robust assemblage of conceptually standardized elements. and validity analysis.

7. **Bibliography**

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